

Deriving Quarks from Lorentz Manifolds – The Rise of 8 Theory

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Abstract:

The following is the original idea which gave rise to the 8-theory, now being studied across the world. The framework, which predicted the value of the fine structure constant using a framework of general relativity, a major step to a final understanding of nature. The theory rose due to this very paper, in the time of writing it, the coupling constant series was out of reach, it was obtained shortly thereafter.

Introduction

Define a Lorentz manifold:

$$\mathbf{s} = (\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (1)$$

Use it to assemble an Euler Lagrange Equation:

$$L = (s, s', t) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{s}} - \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{s}'} = \mathbf{0} \quad (3)$$

Develop the last equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

If the Lorentz manifold to be stationary and no data is attainable from the first three terms, we can require the manifold to those two conditions

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \quad \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (5)$$

If these two are hold to be true, we have areas of extremum curvature on the manifold and negative time invariant acceleration. The demand of extrunum curvature to stay as they are overtime means the acceleration cannot affect them – if so, directed away from them. This in agreement with what we speculate as "dark energy".

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (6)$$

δg As amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \delta g$$

$$\delta g = 0$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Than the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need equal amounts of plus and minuses. The overall amount must be even and summed as zero. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will defy the result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish.

Because of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign. If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$\mathbf{0}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2 \quad (7)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$\mathbf{Y}: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1 \quad (8)$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish. Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps.

So:

- (1(e)1(e)1)
- 2(e)2(e)2
- (221)
- (112)
- (211)
- (122)
- (212)
- (121)

The first two combinations are by the natural maps and one used them to build the other combinations. Overall, there are eight such combinations and additional one arrow combination, which yield (333). Here is how one built it, starting from those two natural maps. (Arrows to variations, colors to pairings):

Therefore, we have Lorenzian manifold with arbitrary variations, which vanish into matter based on that idea. One does not know whether these are the actually variations, as the mathematics does not entail any details about that. Therefore, the graph could be inaccurate in elements order. The colors meant to elements pairing.

References

[1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)